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Ms. Mariana Ávila López
Instituto Politécnico Nacional
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February 15, 2018

Dear Mariana,

I cordially invite you to present your research on the potential use of entomopathogenic nematodes to control mosquito populations in a member symposium titled “Immunological and physiological interactions between insects and pathogens”, which will take place on Saturday, June 23, 2018 in Cancún, Mexico, as part of the 93rd annual meeting of the American Society of Parasitologists. I expect that the symposium will be one of the highlights of the meeting by inciting stimulating discussions and bringing together researchers with common interests on insect-pathogen interactions.

The American Society of Parasitologists, founded in 1924, comprises a diverse group of about 700 scientists from academia, industry, and government involved in the study and teaching of the scientific discipline of parasitology. We look forward to having you take part in what will be an exciting program. Unfortunately, the Society does not have funds to cover the costs associated with your travel or participation, but this meeting always provides good science and good times.

I look forward to seeing you at the ASP meeting in Cancún.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Julian Hillyer". The signature is written in a cursive style with a long horizontal stroke at the end.

Vice-President, American Society of Parasitologists